

Quantum Knapsack : Optimizing Resource Allocation with QAOA

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Abstract—Combinatorial Optimization (CO) is one of the most important areas in the field of optimization, with practical applications found in every industry, including both the private and public sectors, where Efficient scheduling in ship locks is a challenging combinatorial problem. In recent years, it has been discovered that a mathematical formulation known as QUBO (Quadratic Unconstrained Binary Optimization) can encompass an exceptional variety of important CO problems found in industry. In this work, we explore the Quantum Approximate Optimization Algorithm (QAOA) as a quantum computing approach to solve the Knapsack Problem efficiently by formulating the problem as a QUBO model. Here we implemented QAOA on a quantum emulator, leveraging quantum superposition and entanglement to explore multiple solutions simultaneously. The method offers a promising route for solving complex scheduling and resource allocation problems that are tough for classical algorithms, with potential applications in logistics, HPC resource scheduling, and energy optimization.

Index Terms—QAOA, QUBO, Knapsack, Combinatorial Optimization Problems.

1 INTRODUCTION

Combinatorial problems, here specifically knapsack problems, involve finding a grouping, ordering, or assignment of a discrete, finite set of objects that satisfies the given conditions. Due to the nature of the problem, where the computational complexity increases as the number of choices increases, it is necessary to come up with efficient solutions rather than brute force methods. To model this problem we are using QUBO by integrating it into a unified modelling framework. The QUBO model is expressed by the optimization problem:

$$\text{QUBO: } \min / \max y = x^T Q x \quad (1)$$

where x is a vector of binary decision variables and Q is a square matrix of constants. The formulated problem is then passed to QAOA, an algorithm that consists of two main components: a parametric quantum circuit and classical optimization. The first one consists of gates that encode the problem and serve as a potential solution to the optimization problem. Later, the algorithm uses parameters from the quantum gates and performs an iterative optimization to find the best solution.

2 METHODOLOGY AND IMPLEMENTATION

The problem addresses the challenge of optimally filling a shiplock with vessels. The objective is to select ships in a way that maximises the total width S_y , ensuring, that it doesn't exceed the total lock length L_x .

QUBO is utilised for the mathematical formulation of this physical problem. Here y_k are auxiliary binary variables used to model lock position alignment, and C_1, C_2 are penalty weights to enforce constraint satisfaction.

$$\begin{aligned} \max f(x, y) = & \sum_{i=1}^N s_y(i)x_i - C_1 \left(\sum_{i=1}^N s_x(i)x_i - \sum_{k=1}^{L_x} ky_k \right)^2 \\ & - C_2 \left(1 - \sum_{k=1}^{L_x} y_k \right)^2. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

and is encoded into a quantum circuit using QAOA. QAOA aims to minimize the QUBO function eq, where Q is the

Fig. 1: Workflow representing the execution of the problem.

QUBO matrix derived from the formulation 2. The algorithm initiates with the superposition and applies p alternating layers of operations. It consists of two unitaries cost unitary that give a feasible arrangement of ships and mixed unitary which explores the solution space and comes up with all the possible configurations or arrangements. The LR-QAOA lock filling optimisation was implemented using the `pyqubo` library to formulate the multi-knapsack problem as a QUBO, which is then transformed into an equivalent Ising model. Quantum circuit construction and simulation are using the `Qat` (Quantum Application Toolbox) from the `myQLM` framework developed by Eviden. QAOA's parameter sweeps and cost evaluations are naturally parallelizable, and the same optimization loop extends to multiknapsack and multi objective variants by manipulating the QUBO, like tuning penalty weights. The test instance models a single physical lock with $L_x = 20$ m length and $L_y = 10$ m width, arranging 10 ships with varying dimensions and waiting times., as detailed in Table 1. In the implemen-

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TABLE 1: Ship Dataset for LR-QAOA Optimization

Ship ID	Length	Width	Wait (h)	Priority	Size
S0	4	6	10	11.0	Large
S1	3	5	5	7.5	Medium
S2	5	4	8	8.0	Medium
S3	2	7	3	8.5	Large
S4	6	1	7	4.5	Small
S5	8	4	4	6.0	Medium
S6	7	3	3	4.5	Medium
S7	1	5	5	7.5	Medium
S8	2	2	2	3.0	Small
S9	3	6	6	9.0	Large

tation, lock divides into two virtual locks, each treated as a separate knapsack in the multi-knapsack formulation: one for wide ships (width $> 50\%$ of L_y) and one for the remaining ships. This allows LR-QAOA optimization to handle capacity and constraints more effectively for ships of different sizes. Each ship is described by its length (s_x), width (s_y), and waiting time, with a priority value computed as:

$$\text{Priority} = s_y + \alpha \times \text{waiting_time}, \quad \alpha = 0.5$$

The LR-QAOA circuit uses $p = 12$ layers with a linear parameter ramp:

$$\beta_i = \frac{\pi}{4} \left(1 - \frac{i}{p} \right), \quad \gamma_i = \frac{\pi (1 + i)}{4 p}$$

Hadamard gates initialize the superposition, followed by alternating-cost unitaries $U_C(\gamma)$ encoding the Ising Hamiltonian of the QUBO, and mixer unitaries $U_M(\beta)$ implementing X rotations. Constraints are enforced using penalty terms: $C_{\text{assign}} = 20$ (assignment uniqueness), $C_{\text{capacity}} = 20$ (capacity), and $C_{\text{onehot}} = 20$ (slack encoding), with $\text{num}_{\text{slack}} = 4$ binary variables per lock for unused capacity. The circuit was executed on the PyLinalg statevector simulator in myQLM with 5000 shots.

3 RESULTS AND CONCLUSION

The LR-QAOA achieved full lock utilization, placing 8 out of 10 ships without constraint violations, compared to 7 ships by classical greedy and branch-and-bound methods. This gives QAOA a practical advantage: 14% more ships for the same capacity with identical total value (54.50). The valid solution probability of 50.67% is reasonable, since the algorithm explores a superposition of many candidate states and only a subset satisfy all constraints. Despite classical methods having 100% feasibility (7 vs 8 ships), QAOA finds denser packing solutions through quantum exploration.

This work demonstrates that LR-QAOA effectively solves multi-constraint ship placement, achieving full lock utilization and high feasibility. By segmenting multiple knapsacks and size categories, the algorithm ensures capacity and constraint satisfaction while showcasing the efficacy of hybrid quantum-classical scheduling. As shown in Figure 2, LR-QAOA attains near-optimal resource allocation in a complex combinatorial problem, highlighting quantum computing’s potential for maritime logistics and broader operational planning applications. These results also illustrate the promise of hybrid HPC-quantum frameworks for large-scale combinatorial optimization.

Fig. 2: Final lock configuration after applying LR-QAOA optimization.

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